

EFFECTIVENESS OF AYURVEDIC SHAMANA CHIKITSA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SHEETAPITTA (URTICARIA): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Sheetapitta is a *Tridoshaja Twak Vikara* described in *Ayurveda*, commonly correlated with urticaria in modern medicine. It manifests as sudden onset of reddish raised wheals associated with itching, pricking pain, and burning sensation. Exposure to allergens, incompatible diet, faulty lifestyle, and weakened immunity are major causative factors. Conventional management provides temporary symptomatic relief with a high recurrence rate. *Ayurveda* emphasizes *Nidana Parivarjana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* for sustainable management. The present study reports a case of a 30-year-old male patient presenting with classical symptoms of *Sheetapitta*. *Ayurvedic* management including *Haridra Khanda*, *Mahamanjishthadi Kwatha*, *Gandhak Rasayana* for one month, and local application was administered for 15 days. Significant improvement was observed in subjective and objective

parameters without recurrence. This case highlights the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic Shamana Chikitsa* in managing *Sheetapitta*.

KEYWORDS: *Sheetapitta*, Urticaria, *Shamana Chikitsa*, *Kandu*, *Kotha*.

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, *Twak Vikara* (skin disorders) are described as diseases arising from the vitiation of *Doshas*, *Dhatus*, and *Agni*. *Sheetapitta* is one such commonly encountered *Twak Vikara*, characterized by sudden onset of erythematous wheals resembling insect bite, severe itching, pricking pain, and burning sensation.^[1] The term *Sheetapitta* is composed of two words—*Sheeta*, indicating the involvement of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*, and *Pitta*, which denotes the associated burning and inflammatory symptoms.^[2]

According to *Madhava Nidana*, *Sheetapitta* occurs due to exposure to cold breeze (*Sheeta Maruta*), intake of incompatible food (*Viruddha Ahara*), excessive consumption of spicy, sour, salty foods, and contact with allergens.^[3] These etiological factors lead to vitiation of *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha*, which combine with *Pitta Dosha* and circulate throughout the body, lodging in the *Bahya Rogamarga* (skin), thereby manifesting as *Sheetapitta*.^[4] *Madhukosha* commentary states that *Sheetapitta* is a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* with predominance of *Vata Dosha*.^[5]

Clinically, *Sheetapitta* can be correlated with urticaria due to close resemblance in etiopathogenesis and symptomatology.^[6] Urticaria is a common dermatological disorder affecting approximately 20-25% of the population at some point in their lifetime.^[7] It is characterized by transient erythematous wheals with itching caused by mast cell degranulation and release of histamine and other inflammatory mediators.^[8] Although not life-threatening, urticaria significantly affects quality of life and work productivity.^[9]

Modern management mainly involves antihistamines and corticosteroids, which provide temporary relief but are associated with recurrence and adverse effects on prolonged use.^[10] *Ayurveda* offers a holistic approach by addressing the root cause through *Agni Deepana*, *Ama Pachana*, *Dosha Shamana*, and *Rasayana* therapy.^[11] Classical formulations like *Haridra Khanda*, *Gandhak Rasayana*, and *Manjistha*-based preparations are indicated in *Sheetapitta* due to their anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, and blood-purifying properties.^[12,13,14]

The present case study aims to evaluate the efficacy of *Ayurvedic Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Sheetapitta* (urticaria) and to highlight its role as a safe and effective alternative therapy.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To study *Sheetapitta* with reference to urticaria.
2. To assess the efficacy of *Ayurvedic Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Sheetapitta*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Case Report

Study Setting

OPD, Aarogyam Chikitsalay, Nawegaon Bandh, Gondia

Study Period

1 month

Patient Information

- Age: 30 years
- Sex: Male
- Religion: Hindu
- Occupation: Manual worker (loading heavy grain sacks)
- Residence: Rural

History of Present Illness

The patient was apparently healthy 8 days prior to presentation, after which he suddenly developed intense itching all over the body. Raised reddish wheals appeared after 2 days, followed by pricking pain and burning sensation since one day. Symptoms were aggravated after food intake and exposure to environmental allergens at the workplace. Temporary relief was obtained with allopathic medication; however, recurrence occurred after discontinuation.

Past History

History of obesity. No other systemic illness.

Personal History

- Appetite: Regular
- Diet: Mixed (vegetarian and non-vegetarian)
- Bowel habits: Constipation
- Sleep: Irregular
- Addiction: Alcohol, tea, fast food, street food

Nidana (Etiological Factors)

- *Aharaja*: Spicy, oily, fast food, alcohol, *Viruddha Ahara*
- *Viharaja*: Exposure to allergens, heavy physical work
- *Agantuja*: Environmental particles

Purvaroop (Premonitory Symptoms)

- *Aruchi* (loss of appetite)
- *Anga Gaurava* (heaviness)
- *Pipasa* (thirst)

Roop (Clinical Features)

- *Kandu* (severe itching)
- *Kotha* (raised reddish wheals)
- *Toda* (pricking pain)
- *Daha* (burning sensation)

Samprapti

Nidana Sevana leads to *Mandagni* and *Ama* formation. Vitiated *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* combine with *Pitta Dosha* and circulate through *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*. The *Doshas* lodge in *Bahya Rogamarga (Twak)* causing *Sheetapitta*.^[15,16,17]

Examination**General Examination**

- Pulse: 80/min
- BP: 130/80 mmHg
- Temperature: 98°F
- RR: 20/min
- Weight: 90 kg
- Height: 5 ft 2 inch

Clinical Examination (Local)

- Site: Abdomen, back, chest, trunk
- Color: Reddish
- Size: 7-8 cm
- Shape: Irregular patches

- Margins: Raised, irregular
- Temperature: Increased
- Discharge: Absent

Ashtavidha Pariksha

- *Nadi: Pitta-Kapha*
- *Mala: Baddhata*
- *Mutra: Prakrut*
- *Jivha: Saam*
- *Shabda: Spashta*
- *Sparsha: Ushna*
- *Drik: Prakrut*
- *Aakruti: Sthula*

Treatment Protocol

<i>Haridra Khanda</i>	3 g BD	Lukewarm water	1 month
<i>Mahamanjishadi Kwatha</i>	10 ml BD	Lukewarm water	1 month
<i>Gandharva Haritaki</i>	1 capsule HS	Lukewarm water	1 month
<i>Sheetpittabhanjan Rasa</i>	2 tab BD	Lukewarm water	1 month
<i>Gandhak Rasayana</i>	1 tab TDS	Lukewarm water	1 month
<i>Mahamarichadi Taila</i>	Local application B	-	15 day

Pathya: Light diet, avoidance of spicy, oily, junk food and alcohol.

OBSERVATIONS

Improvement in itching and burning sensation was noticed within 7 days. Wheals reduced in size and number gradually. Bowel habits improved.

Image: Erythematous wheals on the skin.

RESULTS

After one month of treatment:

- *Kandu*: Markedly reduced
- *Kotha*: Completely subsided
- *Toda* and *Daha*: Absent
- No recurrence during treatment period

DISCUSSION

Sheetapitta is a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* involving *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu*. *Haridra Khanda* possesses anti-allergic and anti-histaminic properties.^[18] *Mahamanjsthadi Kwatha* acts as *Raktaprasadaka* and *Pittashamaka*.^[19] *Gandharva Haritaki* corrects *Agni* and eliminates *Ama*. *Gandhak Rasayana* provides *Rasayana* and *Kushtaghna* effects. *Mahamarichadi Taila* reduces itching and inflammation. Collectively, these drugs achieved *Samprapti Vighatana* and symptom relief.^[20]

CONCLUSION

This case study demonstrates that *Ayurvedic Shamana Chikitsa* is effective in the management of *Sheetapitta* (urticaria). The holistic approach not only relieved symptoms but also prevented recurrence by correcting underlying *Dosha* imbalance and *Agni*. *Ayurveda* offers a safe and sustainable treatment option for allergic skin disorders.

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